

SKA-Low Substation Templates

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1 Introduction

The SKA telescopes are designed to allow some flexibility in the way elements of the system are combined, to tailor the system to the scientific experiment. The SKA Observatory Establishment and Delivery Plan [AD1] defines subarrays, where only a subdivision of the array is used. Subarrays enable flexibility by allowing individual elements of the array to be combined in different ways, as defined by subarray templates. The first version of subarray templates available to users are provided in [AD2].

Substations refer to beamforming of fewer than the 256 dipole elements within an SKA-Low station, and having the ability to cross-correlate intra- and inter-station beams. Substations afford the user a larger field-of-view, and shorter baselines, providing access to large-scale diffuse structure. Substations are implemented by means of a "weight" term applied to the antennas in a station as each beam is formed, allowing apodization, amplitude tapering, and/or selective omission of antennas in that beam. The current primary science drivers for substations are in the Epoch of Reionisation and Cosmic Dawn (EoR/CD), and Transients science. For EoR/CD, power spectra *near* the end of Reionisation, and tomography *at* the end of Reionisation will have power on spatial scales larger than the field-of-view afforded by a full SKA-Low station. For Transients, the ability to access larger fields-of-view can be used to tile the full sky with tied arrays made from <256 dipoles. Options are presented here that use a combination of subarrays, substations and station beams to tile the sky with different sensitivity/bandwidth trade-offs.

1.1 Purpose of the Document

This document describes substations in order to give the future user an idea of how they might be used. In operations, subarray templates (with and without substation usage) will be available to the user and are further explored in [AD2]. These templates represent the first version of the configurations the SKAO plans to support during operations and serves to enable planning of observations. We encourage feedback from the future user community, ideally directly addressed to members of the Science Operations team at sciops@skao.int.

1.2 Scope of the Document

We present a set of substation templates for SKA-Low that can be applied within a subarray, or across the entire array. The template definitions include the substation average diameter, the number of substations per station, limitations from data rate restrictions, bandwidth, number of baselines available, beam shapes, and field-of-view at key frequencies.

1.3 Impacts of using Substations

Using substations can have impacts on the sidelobes as well as the data rates, and in general:

1. Sidelobes are worse with increasing frequency and for decreasing substation diameters, due to the smaller number of dipoles;
2. Apodization (shaping) of the beams via weights reduces inner sidelobes, but leaves far sidelobes unchanged (or worse);
3. Correlator bandwidth is reduced; for a constant data rate, use of substations may require a reduction in available bandwidth.

2 Substation templates

During the operational phase of SKA-Low, subarray templates [AD2] will be provided to the user community, covering the breadth of configurations required to enable the delivery of high-impact science. Some of these templates will include the provision for substation usage. Version 1 of [AD2] includes only one example subarray template with substations, Low_substation_18m_r1km_AA*, where all of the stations within the inner 1 km are configured with 4, 18m substations (“Low_substation_18m”; described in the following sections). Based on feedback from the community further substation templates will be added.

In this section, 4 example substation configurations are given, using substation average diameters of 18, 12, 9 and 6m. The high-level properties of these substation templates are given in Table 1. During AA* (see [AD5] for a description of the construction timeline) the maximum number of substations is capped at 1440 [AD4], increasing to 2880 during AA4 (baseline design).

In the subsections that follow, further details relating to each template are provided. In each case, beams have been calculated using the average embedded element patterns computed via FEKO¹ simulations [AD6]. Average substation beams were produced by computing the pattern for each substation, and taking the average over the station. The standard deviations of the substation patterns were computed using the same set of patterns. Variability stems from the discretization of the substations, and the differences between the embedded element patterns due to mutual coupling.

Template	D (m)	Substations per station	FoV (150MHz) sr	FoV (tiled) sr	N _{base} per station	Min baseline (m)
Low_substation_18m	18	4	0.012	0.049	6	14.8
Low_substation_12m	12	9	0.028	0.25	36	10.3
Low_substation_9m	9	16	0.049	0.79	120	7.4
Low_substation_6m	6	38	0.111	4.22	703	4.8

Table 1: Broad characteristics of example substation templates. Columns: Template name, substation average diameter, number of substations per regular station, the field-of-view of the

¹ FEKO is a computational electromagnetics simulation tool that calculates accurate complex-valued beam patterns. <https://altair.com/feko>

main beam at 150 MHz, the field-of-view of the sky tiled with N_{sub} beams at 150 MHz, the number of internal baselines within a station, and the minimum baseline length.

2.1 Low_Substation_18m

Four 18m substations can be accommodated within a 39m full station. This configuration would primarily be used in cross-correlation mode for larger FoV and shorter baselines.

Figure 1: Low_Substation_18m template for a station with dipoles oriented North-South. (Top-left) Average XX-polarisation auto-correlation beam at 100 MHz (dB); (bottom-left) standard deviation of the XX auto-correlation beam across substations in the station. Where m , and l are the direction cosines in units of degrees. (Top-right) mapping of dipoles to individual substations; (bottom-right) cut through average auto-correlation beam for XX polarisation, and standard deviation as a function of $\theta = \text{asin}(l)$ and $m=0$, at 100 MHz. Small grey circles denote unused dipoles.

2.2 Low_Substation_12m

Nine 12m substations can be accommodated within a 39m full station. This configuration would primarily be used in cross-correlation mode for larger FoV and shorter baselines.

Figure 2: Low_Substation_12m_r1km_AA* template for a station with dipoles oriented North-South. (Top-left) Average XX-polarisation auto-correlation beam at 100 MHz (dB); (bottom-left) standard deviation of the XX auto-correlation beam across substations in the station. Where m , and l are the direction cosines in units of degrees. (Top-right) mapping of dipoles to individual substations; (bottom-right) cut through average auto-correlation beam for XX polarisation, and standard deviation as a function of $\theta = \text{asin}(l)$ and $m=0$, at 100 MHz. Small grey circles denote unused dipoles.

2.3 Low_Substation_9m

16 9m substations can be accommodated within a 39m full station. The total number of stations that could be configured in this way is $1440/16 = 90$, due to Correlator Beam Former (CBF) restrictions, if all substations were used. This configuration would primarily be used for fly's eye mode where individual beams are used to tile the sky, or a cross-correlation mode within subarrays to tile the desired sky area.

Figure 3: Low_Substation_9m template for a station with dipoles oriented North-South. (Top-left) Average XX-polarisation auto-correlation beam at 100 MHz (dB); (bottom-left) standard deviation of the XX auto-correlation beam across substations in the station. Where m , and l are the direction cosines in units of degrees. (Top-right) mapping of dipoles to individual substations; (bottom-right) cut through average auto-correlation beam for XX polarisation, and standard deviation as a function of $\theta = \text{asin}(l)$ and $m=0$, at 100 MHz. Small grey circles denote unused dipoles.

2.4 Low_Substation_6m

38 6m substations can be accommodated within a 39m full station. The total number of stations that could be configured in this way is $1440/38 = 38$, due to CBF restrictions, if all substations were used. This configuration would primarily be used for fly's eye mode where individual beams are used to tile the sky, or a cross-correlation mode within subarrays to tile the desired sky area.

Figure 4: Low_Substation_6m template for a station with dipoles oriented North-South. (Top-left) Average XX-polarisation auto-correlation beam at 100 MHz (dB); (bottom-left) standard deviation of the XX auto-correlation beam across substations in the station. Where m , and l are the direction cosines in units of degrees. (Top-right) mapping of dipoles to individual substations; (bottom-right) cut through average auto-correlation beam for XX polarisation, and standard deviation as a function of $\theta = \text{asin}(l)$ and $m=0$, at 100 MHz. Small grey circles denote unused dipoles.

3. Correlator and data rate considerations

The use of substations impacts the correlator load and resultant data rates. The load depends on how the substations are used in the overall array. We present three modes of operation:

1. Fully cross-correlated mode ("widefield imaging mode" - high sensitivity)
2. Tied-array mode
3. Cross-correlation with multiple substation beams for sky tiling (low sensitivity).

Restrictions on the CBF and network data rates, yield the following constraints:

- The total number of subarrays cannot exceed 16
- The total number of beams per subarray cannot exceed 48
- The total number of substations across the full array cannot exceed 1440 in AA* (and 2880 in the full baseline design) [AD4].

In addition, there is a bandwidth restriction imposed by the correlator and the network capacity between the stations and the correlator [AD4]. For the bandwidth calculation, we use the scaling:

$$BW_{MHz} = \min(300 \text{ MHz } (512/N_s)^2, 300/N_{sub})$$

where N_s is the number of substations in each subarray and N_{sub} is the number of substations in each full station. The number of baselines includes the auto-correlations, and therefore scales as:

$$N_{base} = N_s(N_s + 1)/2$$

3.1 Widefield Imaging / Tied-array mode

In Table 2 we compute (1) the bandwidth available to the substations assuming that 192 core stations are used, and with a total bandwidth of 300 MHz - note that this assumes that the full 300 MHz bandwidth has been used by the core (i.e., the number of subarrays equals 1); (2) the data rate increase assuming 192 core stations are used for substations with all substations cross-correlated (linear with number of stations; data rate into the correlator); (3) includes CBF limits on total number of available substations for an array release.

Template	N_s	N_{base}	BW available to substations
Low_Substation_18m	768	294,528	75 MHz
Low_Substation_12m	1440	1,036,080	24 MHz
Low_Substation_9m**	1440	1,036,080	24 MHz
Low_Substation_6m**	1440	1,036,080	24 MHz

Table 2: Approximate available bandwidth (column 4) for the four substation templates given in Section 2, here N_s is the number of substations in each subarray (assumed to be one subarray in this case) and N_{base} is the total number of baselines in the subarray. In each case it is assumed that substations are formed within the central 192 stations, all substations are cross- and auto-correlated, and the remainder of the array is unused. This keeps the data rate constant by reducing the bandwidth available to the substations. **The 9m and 6m configurations might not be expected to be cross-correlated; but instead be used in fly's eye mode to tile the sky. Data rate assumptions are based on the correlator operating with a 0.849s integration time.

3.2 Cross-correlated sky tiling mode

In this mode, the array is split into the maximum number of 16 subarrays, with each subarray forming the number of station beams required to tile the sky (up to a maximum of 48 per subarray). The substations within each subarray are internally cross-correlated, and the 48 resulting beams per subarray are used to tile part of the sky. The sky area for each beam is given by the substation primary beam response. The total number of baselines is given by:

$$N_{base} = \frac{16}{2} \left(N \frac{N_{sub}}{16}\right) \left(N \frac{N_{sub}}{16} + 1\right)$$

where N is the number of full stations being used, N_{sub} is the number of substations per station, and we have assumed 16 subarrays that are internally cross-correlated. Table 3 provides the number of baselines, station beams and maximum bandwidth of these configurations assuming use of $N=192$ core stations. The available bandwidth differs from Table 2 due to only internal substations within a given subarray being cross-correlated in Table 3, compared with all substations in Table 2 (1 subarray). This allows for greater bandwidth availability.

Template	N_s	N_{base}	N_{beams}	Bandwidth (MHz) ²
Low_Substation_18m	768	18,816	256	136 MHz
Low_Substation_12m	1440	<94,176	112	>60.6 MHz
Low_Substation_9m*	1440	<296,448	64	>34.2 MHz
Low_Substation_6m*	1440	<1,667,136	32	>11.8 MHz

Table 3: Configurations for a cross-correlated mode using subarrays and station multi-beaming to tile the sky. For configurations limited by the total number of allowable substations, the actual number of baselines will be smaller and the available bandwidth larger. Assumes 16 subarrays with internal cross-correlation and auto-correlations, pi radians of sky covered at 150 MHz, and 192 core stations only. The number of beams is scaled to meet the required sky area coverage.

² Assumes 300MHz total BW for each subarray, and then BW split across the station beams.

References

A.1 Applicable Documents

The following documents are applicable to the extent stated herein. In the event of conflict between the contents of the applicable documents and this document, **the applicable documents** shall take precedence.

- [AD1] SKA-TEL-SKO-0001722 version 03, Observatory Establishment and Delivery Plan
- [AD2] SKAO-TEL-0002380, SKA Low and Mid Subarray Templates
- [AD3] SKA-TEL-SKO-0000120, SKA1 Configuration Management Plan
- [AD4] SKA-TEL-AIV-4410001, Rollout Plan for SKA1-Low
- [AD5] SKAO-TEL-0002299 version 2, SKAO staged delivery, array assemblies and layouts
- [AD6] Bolli et al., Journal of Astronomical Telescopes, Instruments, and Systems, Volume 8, id. 011017 (2022), DOI [10.1117/1.JATIS.8.1.011017](https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JATIS.8.1.011017)

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AA	Array Assembly
AD	Applicable Document
CBF	Correlator Beam Former
CD	Cosmic Dawn
EoR	Epoch of Reionisation
FoV	Field of View
RD	Reference Document
SKA	Square Kilometre Array
SKAO	SKA Observatory

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Revision	Date Of Issue	Engineering Change Number	Comments
01	2024-08-20		1 st Release

DOCUMENT SOFTWARE

	Package	Version	Filename
Word processor	MS Word	Office 365	SKAO-TEL-0002390-01_SKA Low Substation Template.docx
Block diagrams			
Other			

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